

CARE IN SITUATIONS OF SUICIDE

THE PSYCHOLOGIST'S ROLE AMONG BEREAVED PARENTS

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SUMMARY

With the theme of the psychological clinic in suicide situations, more specifically, of the performance of the psychologist with bereaved parents, we intend to defend that the formation in psychology favors a differentiated knowledge and experience, which allows a specific clinical treatment with bereaved parents. Themes such as death, mourning and psychological clinic will be developed through a review of the literature. In conclusion, we intend to defend that there is the possibility of a psychological practice beyond the manuals that dictate the behaviors that must be expressed in these situations. To go beyond the manuals means to accompany the experience of mourning without jargon or merely technical symbolism, that is, to be able to, in the experience of mourning, through serenity and patience, to remain together with pain or suffering, sustaining the possibility of a transforming action.

KEYWORDS

Death; mourning; suicide; clinical psychology.

RESUMO

Com o tema do cuidado em situações de suicídio, mais especificamente, o da atuação do psicólogo junto a pais enlutados, pretendemos defender a necessidade de um conhecimento e experiência diferenciados de outros saberes, no entanto, não prescindindo deles. Temas como a morte, o luto e a clínica psicológica são contemplados. Em conclusão, pretendemos defender a possibilidade de uma prática psicológica para além dos manuais que ditam os comportamentos do profissional que devem ser expressos nessas situações. Ir além significa poder acompanhar a experiência de luto sem jargões ou simbolismos meramente técnicos, ou seja, poder, na própria experiência de luto, em uma atitude de cuidado: serena e paciente, permanecer junto à dor ou ao sofrimento, sustentando a possibilidade de um momento epifânico.

PALAVRAS-CHAVE

Morte; luto; suicídio; clínica psicológica.

INTRODUCTION

WHO (2017) says that in each death by suicide, there are on average six people close to them, be they family, friends or those who witnessed the scene, who are affected in their different scopes: affective, emotional, social and economic.

Considering that approximately 804,000 people die each year from suicide and that by 2020 this rate can increase by up to 50%, surpassing in great numbers the deaths by homicide and due to war, we are faced with an alarming public health problem. Since around 1.2 million people will die by suicide in 2020 and that about six people per death will be affected, we conclude that some 7,200,000 individuals will suffer from the sequelae from voluntary deaths.

At the moment we are faced with an alarming situation: that of the survivors. According to the **CFP** (2013), survivor is the usual term in suicidology to refer to those who attempted suicide in a way that did not die, either by a simple joke of fate or, furthermore, to relatives who survived despite the voluntary death of a of the family. Statistical data released by the World Health Organization (WHO, 2006) report that for each suicide attempt five to ten people are affected in terms of social, emotional and economic. WHO (2014) and the American Association for the Prevention of Suicide (2018) have manuals for the professionals involved with bereaved families.

In the psychological consultations addressed to these relatives, we find that they insist on asking what they did wrong, why they had not seen the warnings, how they should have proceeded, etc. Some also refer to shame and the difficulty of resuming their work tasks. In failed suicide attempts, many family members take on the task of monitoring, controlling, and even policing the survivor. With this, their life projects are relegated to second place. These behaviors indicate that it is necessary not only to follow, psychologically, those who think of suicide, but also that it was necessary to give more attention to relatives. To do so, we must first deepen our studies and research on the subject of survivors.

There is an effort by the scientific community and even by lay people to prevent suicide and its consequences. The World Health Organization's Department of Mental and Substance Abuse and Mental Disorders and Nervous System Diseases (WHO, 2017) recommends promoting self-help groups for survivors in order to share useful information on suicide and the experience of mourning. The groups have advisors who offer not only comfort but also opportunity for the mourners to process their feelings of guilt, anger and deep sadness. In addition, they should inform them about post-suicide care, so that there is an understanding of mental illness as something that potentiates the

suicidal act, thereby providing them with relief from stress and guilt. In this way, counselors work towards a healthy recovery for the survivors, reducing the tendency towards imitation and contagion (Suicide prevention a resource for counselors, WHO, 2016).

Certainly, counselors who receive training to accompany those who survived the suicide of a close person are helpful for two reasons: 1- We still do not have professionals from different fields of study to deal with the issue of suicide and its surroundings; 2 - the service centers are still insufficient to meet the demand, given the large contingent of people affected by the suicide act. These same reasons led us, in the previous research, to create a Clinical Care Center for those who think of suicide (Feijoo, 2018), and to prepare professionals and students of psychology to perform clinical care with the scientific and instrumental bases of psychology. Still for these same reasons, we will follow the research on suicide, now promoting studies on the possibility of a psychological clinic aimed at survivors, more specifically, parents. We want to seek the basis of a practice based on studies and qualitative research so that we can sustain a clinical action with professionals of psychology properly prepared for the psychological assistance to parents. We are interested in not only telling what is done and for what, but how it is done, clarifying, in detail, how the practice is performed, always emphasizing the scientific nature of the obtained results.

Why choose psychological counseling only to parents, not children, siblings or other family members? Accompanying different reports on the subject, which in addition to focusing more on parents than on any other family, have a surprising reaction to the suicide of their children. They make it very clear in their reports that they wish to do the same as the child and refer to the fact that life has lost its meaning. They end up feeling guilty, resentful, lonely and unsuccessful. It becomes clear what MS (2009) calls the risk of contagion, that is, when one family commits suicide, it mobilizes the other to wish to do the same. We can follow the situation of parents bereaved by the suicide of their children in excerpts from the following reports.

In the magazine "Época" from 16/04/2018, we'll find a report titled, "The pain without name", which reported about survivors of suicide that coexist with a peculiar suffering, loaded with loneliness and guilt. Tavares (2018) deals with the subject, reporting the mother's guilt, Terezinha, of a 19-year-old girl who committed the act six months ago, at a short time when her parents went to a funeral. She had promised that she would not do it on the basis that she did not want to feel pain. She said: "Hanging and cutting me hurts, throwing myself through the window hurts" (p.62). After the episode, the mother reports the feeling of failure, loneliness and the estrangement of friends and family. It says: "The worst part is not seeing the child in the coffin. It's learning to live without the child. " (p.63).

And another time: "Now I understand why I am a survivor. You feel like a loser, you have a lot of feelings you do not know how to deal with. He looks to the side and is alone" (p.63). Later Terezinha, showing guilt, says: "Why did I trust that she was well ?, Why did not I realize?". "If I had the chance to go back in time to appreciate more the signs she was giving, that it was not just an old problem but a real pain, I would come back" (2018, 47). It is not surprising that this mother feels this way, because after all scientific research, it points to family conflicts as one of the causes of suicide. And, even more so, because suicide prevention manuals categorically state that the act can be avoided in most cases, it is enough for relatives to heed the clues as most suicides leave clues. The indication is that constant monitoring is maintained. Terezinha refers to her desire to do the same as her Marina did. On the other hand, it appears in other reports the resentment of the parents by the attitude of the suicidal son, as we can follow in the following report: "Was I not enough for the person to want to remain alive?" (P.47).

In the magazine "Isto É" from May 2nd, 2018, the story entitled "Dreams Interrupted", a report by Vicente Vilardaga and Georgia Cavicchioli (2018), with the subtitle "Covert Feelings" notices the suicide of two young men of 16 and 17 years. Neither of them were victims of bullying, both had friends, parents were present in their lives and were good students. Therefore, anything that is

scored as a risk factor was not present in the behavior of the boys. We suppose that this is why the report has as subtitle the denomination of "Covert feelings" (page 46). We also think about what we still need to know about the phenomenon. We insist that when we work with indicators a priori we lose sight of other mobilizers of the act.

Another element that needs to be revised is the information that most suicides leave clues. Ivo, referring to the suicide of his 18-year-old daughter, says: "That day, we had our usual lunch at a restaurant. The only thing she did differently was ordering a mango juice instead of orange. She gave no sign that she intended to take her own life, she was normal, she had finished high school and was taking a college entrance exam" (p. 48). The aforementioned reports, as they highlight the story of bereaved parents, as well as the experience of psychologist Karina Okajima Fukumitsu (2015, 2016) with bereaved parents, make it clear that mourning for the death of their children by suicide is a more complex phenomenon than a simple description of the signs to be observed and that exercising constant vigilance is insufficient to deal with the issue. This is one of the reasons why we decided to investigate the subject: A Psychologist's Role among Bereaved Parents.

ABOUT MOURNING

With regards to mourning, there was a significant change in the passage from DSM IV (APA, 1995) to DSM V (APA, 2014). Mourning was excluded as a diagnosis of major depression. With this change, it is no longer medicated (Pies, 2014).

Undoubtedly, this amendment brought a deep discussion on the subject. Freitas (2018), referring to current studies on mourning, makes the following caveat: "Understanding mourning has undergone profound changes in its theoretical and practical aspects, with important repercussions in the recent version of DSM". The author refers to two important impacts in this new version, which are: the normal mourning and the mourning with commitment. This scholar adopts a critical attitude towards the positioning of the manual and argues that there is no a priori understanding of experience as out of normality. The studies on mourning are fundamental so that we can understand their specificities in the mourning for suicide. Freitas (2013) as the psychological literature presents this experience: "[...] as a reaction against significant losses" (p.97). The author, imbued with the phenomenological perspective, sends a comprehensive proposal of the experience of mourning and refers to the experience as that of a self without you (p.99).

The idea of mourning and loss can also be found in another scholar of the subject, Esslinger (2008), referring to the link that breaks irreversibly, that is, recognizes it as something of the order of existence and, therefore, should not be accompanied as a disease to be treated by medicines, but what matters is the experience of mourning.

Brice (1991), an American phenomenologist who studied the experience of mourning, investigated the maternal mourning, suspending all the previous theories that speak of the subject, whether they come from the natural sciences or from the psychodynamic theories. Brice questions that the mourning is placed in the category of a pathology, having time as a criteria, which according to the current theories, is six months. From this period on, mourning begins to be interpreted as pathological. The American phenomenologist, carried out his research with three bereaved mothers and concluded that maternal mourning is something that can not be determined by time, that is, something that is not a disease and therefore has no cure and positions the units of meaning which appeared in the three reports of mourning mothers. These are: the experience of an interrupted project; the impression that the child may arrive at any moment; the feeling of imputation, among others.

Parkes (1998) addresses mourning from death by suicide, which has very peculiar characteristics. Relatives refer to guilt and debt. Martins & Leo (2010) add to this the shame and the revolt at the suicidal act of one of the family members.

To think about grief, we will take human experience as portrayed by literature. Adélia Prado (1991) interprets mourning from the perspective of memory, not as representation, but as an experience of longing. Lígia Bojunga (2006) also refers to mourning as nostalgia and says that despite it, life goes on and can have moments of great joy.

THE PSYCHOLOGICAL CLINIC WITH BEREAVED PARENTS

Clinical practice, as we understand it, that is, from an existential perspective, requires that we first conquer all non-moralizing view of suicide. There is no place for us to think of the perpetrator of the act and its relatives by means of pathological categories, nor of stereotypes (Feijoo, 2017). In this respect, we approach Critchley's (2015) inspired by Hume, in which suicide is taken without moral judgment and without despair.

In the first part of the research, that is, in the center of clinical care, we highlight important aspects to be addressed in the

consultations: indecision of those who ask for help, affective bonds, resentments that needed to be amended, etc. (Feijoo, 2018). In this second stage, we defend that it is up to the psychologist to be close to the mourner, patiently, waiting for his thinking aloud, his pain. Bereaved parents speak of their lack, longing, amputation and vulnerability. It is up to us to sustain the space of pain so that it can be shown in all its power. And thus, the mourner when perceiving himself understood, can see that he has a space to share his pain. The clinical relationship supports the possibility of a will-power that is made by listening and obedience.

It is up to the psychologist to follow what the mourner has to tell him so that he can break the bonds of illusion, after all, it may be that pain is inevitable. The insane struggle in trying to escape pain is suffering and it ends when we stop fighting and accept that life and pain are inseparable. Parents often refuse to have their projects interrupted. At other times they are filled with resentment, indignation, frustration, and talk of it all through lamentation. Here we have a clinical space where the saying of the clinic is an exercise in the awakening of what the parents have forgotten, because they are accustomed to the idea of death as one that will not happen yet, as being only for others, something impersonal, controllable and postponable. The will of the parents is a will that sees itself sovereign, without surrender, without listening in obedience. It is necessary to evoke the experience of listening, of surrendering to your destiny.

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